

STUDY OF MINERAL SUBSTANCES IN EASILY DIGESTIBLE RABBIT MEAT

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Abstract. *Minerals play a major role in the biochemical processes occurring in the body, determine the state of the blood circulation system and muscle contractions, and are a necessary component of all organs and tissues. They enter the body only with food and therefore are essential components of nutrition. Minerals do not have energy value, but are necessary for the functioning of the body. They enter the body with food in the form of mineral salts. Minerals contained in food products and body tissues in significant quantities are classified as microelements.*

Microelements are basic and acidic in nature. The basic ones include calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium, and the acidic ones include phosphorus, sulfur, and chlorine. The rabbit meat a white meat which contains macro nutrients and micro nutrients and it is a good source of minerals entering the human body is food products of plant and animal origin. Drinking water covers only up to 10% of the daily requirement for microelements such as J, Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Mo, and only for individual microelements (F, Sr) can it serve as the main source of their intake into the body. The content of various microelements in the diet depends on the geochemical conditions of the area in which the products were obtained, as well as on the set of food products included in the diet.

Keywords: *mineral substances, food products, meat products, macro and microelements.*

Annotatsiya. *Minerallar organizmda sodir bo'ladigan biokimyoviy jarayonlarda katta rol o'ynaydi, qon aylanish tizimining holatini va mushaklarning qisqarishini belgilaydi va barcha organlar va to'qimalarning zarur tarkibiy qismidir. Ular tanaga faqat oziq-ovqat bilan kiradi va shuning uchun ovqatlanishning muhim tarkibiy qismlari hisoblanadi. Minerallar energiya qiymatiga ega emas, lekin tananing ishlashi uchun zarurdir. Ular tanaga mineral tuzlar shaklida oziq-ovqat bilan kiradi. Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari va tana to'qimalarida katta miqdorda mavjud bo'lgan minerallar mikroelementlar deb tasniflanadi. Mikroelementlar asosli va kislotali tabiatga ega. Asosiy moddalarga kaltsiy, magniy, kaliy, natriy, kislotalilarga esa fosfor, oltingugurt va xlor kiradi. Quyon go'shti oq go'sht bo'lib, tarkibida makro va mikroelementlar mavjud bo'lib, u inson tanasiga kiradigan minerallarning yaxshi*

manbai bo'lib, o'simlik va hayvonlardan olingan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari hisoblanadi. Ichimlik suvi J, Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Mo kabi mikroelementlarga bo'lgan kunlik ehtiyojning atigi 10 foizini qoplaydi va faqat alohida mikroelementlar (F, Sr) uchun ularni qabul qilishning asosiy manbai bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin. tanasi. Ratsiondagi turli mikroelementlarning tarkibi mahsulot olingan hududning geokimyoviy sharoitlariga, shuningdek, dietaga kiritilgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari to'plamiga bog'liq.

Kalit soʻzlar: mineral moddalar, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari, go'sht mahsulotlari, makro va mikroelementlar.

Аннотация. Минералы играют важную роль в биохимических процессах, происходящих в организме, определяют состояние системы кровообращения и мышечных сокращений, являются необходимым компонентом всех органов и тканей. Они попадают в организм только с пищей и поэтому являются важными компонентами питания. Минералы не имеют энергетической ценности, но необходимы для функционирования организма. Они поступают в организм с пищей в виде минеральных солей. Минеральные вещества, содержащиеся в пищевых продуктах и тканях организма в значительных количествах, относятся к микроэлементам. Микроэлементы имеют основную и кислую природу. К основным относятся кальций, магний, калий, натрий, а к кислым – фосфор, сера и хлор. Мясо кролика – белое мясо, которое содержит макронутриенты и микроэлементы и является хорошим источником минеральных веществ, поступающих в организм человека, – это пищевые продукты растительного и животного происхождения. Питательная вода покрывает лишь до 10% суточной потребности в таких микроэлементах, как J, Cu, Zn, Mn, Co, Mo, и только для отдельных микроэлементов (F, Sr) она может служить основным источником поступления их в организм. тело. Содержание различных микроэлементов в рационе зависит от геохимических условий местности, в которой были получены продукты, а также от набора продуктов питания, входящих в рацион.

Ключевые слова: минеральные вещества, пищевые продукты, мясные продукты, макро и микроэлементы.

Introduction

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the influence of diet on human health and well-being. The primary role of diet is to provide sufficient nutrients to meet the nutritional requirements of an individual [1]. There is now increasing scientific evidence to support the hypothesis that some foods and food components have beneficial physiological and psychological effects over and above the provision of the basic nutrients. Many traditional foods contain components with potential meat quality and safety 1289 health benefits. In addition to these foods, new foods are

being developed to enhance or incorporate these beneficial components due to their health benefits or desirable physiological effects. The healthy lifestyle and healthy food are a hot topic of humans everyday life, containing the area of production and raw materials processing, distribution, and consumption [2]. Because of a great availability and variability of foods on the market, there is also great competition between producers to offer products of the highest quality products to consumers. Regarding the meat market, rabbit meat is not prevalent worldwide and its consumption is presently regressing, despite of the high nutritional and dietetic properties of rabbit meat [3], except for countries where it is considered a traditional meat species. This rabbit meat-eating habits can be changed to positive side and encouraged more people to consume rabbit meat by increasening of its quality due to its improved nutritional properties—fatty acid (FA) and amino acid (AA) profile, minerals, and vitamin content [4].

We do canned products as a pate and stew based rabbit meat and adding antioxidants in our laboratory condition. Pate a shell of mostly cylindrical dough for spicy stew, a dish of minced meat, baked in a shell of dough or served in a terrine an exquisite snack dish in the form of a viscous homogeneous pasty mass of boiled or fried and then pureed meat. After producing product has given following results of mineral substances from the content of finished products based rabbit meat [5].

Fig 1. Preparation of finished product from rabbit meat

The mineral fraction of rabbit meat is characterized by its low contents in sodium (300 and 450 mg/100 g for hind leg and loin, respectively) and iron (1.3 and 1.1 mg/100 g for hind leg and loin, respectively), while. Rabbit meat has a high zinc concentration (20 and 25 mg/100 g) and the copper concentration is quite similar to the meat of other species (10 and 14 mg/100 g and 22 µg/100 g). After preparation the product has given following results of mineral substances from the content of finished products with antioxidants based rabbit meat [6].

Table 1 Mineral substances in rabbit meat

Minerals	Authorized document	Stew	Pate 1	Pate 2
Copper	USSR EH 14084-2014	11,32	13,41	13,48
Zinc	USSR EH 14084-2015	24,11	20,15	19,74
Iron	USSR EH 14084-2016	26,77	34,96	52,9
Sodium	USSR ISO 8070/IDF 119	404,4	395,7	420,5
Potassium	USSR ISO 8070/IDF 119	3469,9	3512,4	3387,4
Calcium	USSR ISO 8070/IDF 119	41	116	64,95
Magnesium	USSR ISO 8070/IDF 119	268,4	225,7	163,6

Conclusion

The rabbit meat a white meat which contains macro nutrients and micro nutrients and it is a good source of minerals entering the human body is food products of plant and animal origin. The content of various microelements in the diet depends on the geochemical conditions of the area in which the products were obtained, as well as on the set of food products included in the diet.

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